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A quasi-experimental evaluation of a research grant program: the tale of varied results based on different outcome variables, analysis periods, and estimation methods¹

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Introduction

This paper presents the evaluation of the “Lider” program founded by the Polish National Centre for Research and Development. Lider is a prestigious research grant program for young scientists (up to 35 years old) aimed primarily at those studying natural and applied sciences. This analysis focuses on the first four editions of Lider (2011, 2012, 2013, and 2014) and its 142 laureates and 290 unsuccessful participants.

The research contributes to the literature primarily by presenting a comparison of evaluation results based on (a) various outcome variables (16 outcome variables), (b) different timeframes of analyses (6), and (c) three quasi-experimental methods: difference-in-differences (DID), propensity score matching (PSM), and regression discontinuity design (RDD). The analysis shows that conclusions based on different combinations of the above-mentioned dimensions (a-b-c) can differ extensively and that only selected effects persist over most of the variants. This is a warning signal for policymakers, policy analysts, and evaluators because decisions regarding the scope and methods of the study turn out to have a major impact on the results of the evaluation.

Data and descriptive statistics

Our main data sources are as follows:

- administrative data from Polish National Centre for Research and Development
- Web of Science (publications, citations, international cooperation)
- Scopus (publications, citations)

¹ This work was supported by the Polish National Centre for Research and Development.

- Google Scholar (publications, citations)
- Database of the Polish Patent Office (patent applications)
- POL-on Databases (patents granted, grants awarded, prizes awarded)

Table 1 presents the outcome variables used in the analysis. In some analyses (DID and PSM), these variables are also used as independent variables, primarily to characterize applicants before the competition.

Table 1 Outcome variables

Code	Description	Measured aspect
n_art_wos	Number of publications on Web of Science—whole counts	Productivity
n_art_wos_f	Number of publications on Web of Science—fractional counts	Productivity
n_art_scopus	Number of publications on Scopus—whole counts	Productivity
n_art_scopus_f	Number of publications on Scopus—fractional counts	Productivity
n_art_gs	Number of publications on Google Scholar	Productivity
avg_cit_wos_norm	The average number of citations according to Web of Science normalized in fields and years	Quality
avg_cit_scopus_norm	The average number of citations according to Scopus normalized in fields and years	Quality
avg_cit_gs_norm	The average number of citations according to Google Scholar normalized in fields and years	Quality
art_wos_int	U publication department in international cooperation (based on Web of Science)	Internationalization
mnisw_wos_avg	The average number of points according to the list of Ministry of Science and Higher Education journals for articles identified in the Web of Science	Quality
mnisw_scopus_avg	The average number of points according to the list of Ministry of Science and Higher Education journals for articles identified in Scopus	Quality
n_pat	Number of patents according to the Patent Office of the Republic of Poland	Productivity
any_pat	At least one patent UP RP	Productivity
n_pat_pol	Number of patents according to POL-on	Productivity
n_proj	Number of scientific grants (projects) according to POL-on	Productivity
n_nagr	Number of awards according to POL-on	Quality

Source: Own study.

The next two tables (2 and 3) present the average values, or shares, of the control and outcome variable. Table 2 also contains success rates for individual categories. In the studied population there are stark differences in terms of gender (greater representation of men than women, including higher success rate for men), type of institution (large branch of universities, negligible enterprises), fields of science (most grants awarded concern technical sciences, a small percentage of sciences social and natural). Variables regarding the profiles of applicants on research portals (Google Scholar, ResearchGate, and Academia.edu) show that successful applicants care more about their online image than unsuccessful applicants do.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics and success rate by category

	Successful	Unsuccessful	Success rate (%)
	Share or average	Share or average	
Age (in the year of competition)	33.15 (SD: 2.24) ^(a)	33.36 (SD: 3.61)	Not applicable
Sex:			
Woman	0.26	0.38	25.2
Man	0.74	0.62	36.8
Profile in:			
Google Scholar	0.54	0.49	35.0
+ photo	0.28	0.24	36.4
ResearchGATE	0.85	0.72	36.6
+ photo	0.61	0.50	37.3
Academia.edu	0.37	0.34	34.6
+ photo	0.11	0.08	39.5
Competition (last participation):			
LEADER I	0.16	0.25	24.2
LEADER II	0.25	0.24	33.6
LEADER III	0.27	0.26	33.9
LEADER IV	0.32	0.25	38.1
Institution type:			
University	0.67	0.18	33.1
Research Institute (JBR)	0.15	0.14	28.4
Polish Academy of Sciences	0.15	0.66	34.9
Company	0.03	0.01	50.0
Field ^(b) :			
Social s. and humanities	0.01	0.11	6.2
Technical	0.61	0.48	38.1
Medical	0.13	0.07	33.9
Agricultural	0.07	0.11	34.5
Exact sciences	0.15	0.13	38.9
Natural sciences	0.03	0.10	11.4

^(a) SD—standard deviation.

^(b) Fields were assigned based on the classification used in the application form; the humanities and social sciences have been combined into one category because of the low number of applications attributed to the humanities.

Source: Own study.

Table 3. The values of outcome variables within five years before the year of the competition (pre ...) and five years from the year of the competition (post ...)

	Successful		Unsuccessful	
	Average	SD ^(a)	Average	SD ^(a)
pre_n_art_wos	10.11	9.77	5.38	9.54
post_n_art_wos	13.22	11.58	7.06	9.51
pre_n_art_wos_f	2.65	2.53	1.43	1.74
post_n_art_wos_f	3.41	3.01	2.01	2.38
pre_n_art_scopus	11.82	11.30	5.98	10.09
post_n_art_scopus	14.32	11.65	7.50	9.56
pre_n_art_scopus_f	3.18	2.89	1.70	2.02
post_n_art_scopus_f	3.88	3.39	2.22	2.54
pre_n_art_gs	20.04	13.55	15.65	12.52
post_n_art_gs	22.58	14.11	17.31	14.11
pre_avg_cit_wos_norm	1.49	2.06	0.86	1.60
post_avg_cit_wos_norm	1.36	1.49	0.86	1.41
pre_avg_cit_scopus_norm	1.41	1.74	0.89	1.65
post_avg_cit_scopus_norm	1.29	1.36	0.90	1.47
pre_avg_cit_gs_norm	1.38	1.27	0.85	0.99
post_avg_cit_gs_norm	1.27	1.35	0.87	1.28
pre_art_wos_int	0.31	0.34	0.23	0.33
post_art_wos_int	0.23	0.25	0.21	0.28
pre_mnisw_wos_avg	28.56	7.15	27.84	7.89
post_mnisw_wos_avg	28.85	6.48	27.27	7.16
pre_mnisw_scopus_avg	27.39	7.49	26.15	8.58
post_mnisw_scopus_avg	28.06	7.05	25.46	8.20
pre_n_pat	1.27	2.49	0.33	1.04
post_n_pat	2.51	4.60	0.66	1.92
pre_any_pat (udział)	0.38	-	0.16	-
post_any_pat (udział)	0.58	-	0.24	-
pre_n_pat_pol	0.06	0.36	0.02	0.19
post_n_pat_pol	0.99	2.21	0.25	0.91
pre_n_proj	0.40	0.67	0.24	0.73
post_n_proj	0.94	1.27	0.70	1.25
pre_n_nagr	0.08	0.51	0.03	0.23
post_n_nagr	1.37	4.19	0.67	4.24

^(a) SD—standard deviation.

^(b) Contextual variable—not studied as a variable explained in the following quasi-experimental analyses .

Source: Own study.

The values of the outcome variables in Table 3 testify to the vast differences between the successful and unsuccessful applicants, both before and after the outcome of the Leader competition. The differences between these groups are statistically significant (at least $p < 0.1$) for almost all variables. The only exceptions—i.e., statistically insignificant differences—relate to the number of prizes (n_proj) in the period before and after, the percentage of articles with co-authors from abroad in the period after (post_art_wos_int), and two indicators in the period before competition: the average number of points according to the list of Ministry of Science and Higher Education journals (pre_mnisw_wos_avg and pre_mnisw_scopus_avg) and the

number of patents according to POL-on (pre_n_pat_pol). The direction of differences in the values of explained variables indicates a clear advantage for successful applicants, both before and after obtaining the Leader grant. This means, firstly, that applicants with more achievements have qualified for the program. Secondly, the differences identified may suggest a positive impact of the program on the effects of the scientific activities of its beneficiaries. Such a conclusion, however, is premature and unjustified. Table 3 presents the so-called "first differences", i.e., it does not include endogenous differences between the compared groups. In particular, the clear variation between groups before the settlement of the competition may mean that the differences identified after the settlement are a continuation of the earlier differentiation rather than an indication of the impact of the grant. To separate the possible impact of the program from the "naturally" occurring differentiation between the groups, three variants of quasi-experimental analysis were carried out.

Variants of timeframes of analysis

Annual data (see example below) show interesting differences and trends, but they are not very well suited for modelling program effects. This is for two reasons. First, data points can be very few in individual years. As a result, annual averages are characterized by high volatility, to some extent having a random character, such as when they result from the publication of an article in December or January. The low number of data points is particularly visible in the years before the results of the competitions, which in turn results from the fact that a few years before the competition applicants were starting their scientific careers. Secondly, many processes in scientific work last much longer than one year (e.g., the publication cycle—lasting from the research idea to the publication of the results—is typically calculated in years rather than months).

Figure 1. Exemplary annual data—the number of patents filed

Source: Own study.

Designating the comparative periods before and after the competition Leader is not a trivial task. There are three aspects to consider: (1) the definition of "year zero"—i.e., the moment when the first effects can be expected; (2) identification of the minimum and the maximum possible range of years; and (3) choice of length of periods. In analogous quasi-experimental

Conclusions

A summary of the results of quasi-experimental analyses is presented in Table 5 below. The analysis provides strong evidence that the Leader program has an impact on the patent activity of its beneficiaries. The effect is essentially substantive: the receipt of a grant translates into one additional patent application (and patent received) within five years of the competition results (on average in the population of successful applicants). The obtained results also suggest an impact on the increase in the number of publications, but this effect is most pronounced in the case of the group of applicants who had the lowest chance of obtaining a Leader grant (LATE: Local Average Treatment Effect). It should be emphasized, however, that the parameters for insignificant variants of the analysis are consistently positive, which may suggest that with greater precision of estimation (e.g., with a larger sample and an extended study period) the effect could exceed the conventional statistical significance thresholds. The situation is slightly different in the case of received awards. Here, too, a positive local effect is observable (i.e., for applicants who had the lowest chance of obtaining a Leader grant). However, in other variants of the analysis, the estimated parameters are unstable, sometimes negative, and sometimes positive, which suggests that there is no effect across the entire population (except LATE) and that increasing the sample would only confirm the absence of this effect. For all other output variables, there is no reason to claim that the examined program has an impact.

This research contributes to the literature primarily by presenting a comparison of the evaluation results based on various outcome variables, different timeframes of analyses, and three quasi-experimental methods. The analysis shows that conclusions based on different combinations of the above-mentioned dimensions can differ extensively and that only selected effects persist over most of the variants. This is a warning signal for policymakers, policy analysts, and evaluators because decisions regarding the scope and methods of the study turn out to have a major impact on the results of the evaluation.

Table 5. Summary of quasi-experimental analyses

Method:	DID						PSM						RDD*						Conclusions
Effect tested:	ATT**						ATT**						LATE***						
Sample:	432						393						160						
A variant of the period:	T/0/5	T/1/5	T/0/4	T/1/4	T/0/3	T/1/3	T/0/5	T/1/5	T/0/4	T/1/4	T/0/3	T/1/3	T/0/5	T/1/5	T/0/4	T/1/4	T/0/3	T/1/3	
n_art_wos							+	+					+	+	+	+	+	The impact of the program on publishing activity was visible primarily for one method (RDD). For other methods, the positive impact was relatively consistently visible, but the estimation was not statistically significant.	
n_art_wos_f																			
n_art_scopus							+	+					+		+	+	+		
n_art_scopus_f																			
n_art_gs							NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
avg_cit_wos_norm																		The impact on citations was seen in a small number of variants. The estimated parameters were inconsistently differentiated. This suggests that there is no link between the receipt of the Leader grant and the number of citations to publications published after the outcome of the competition.	
avg_cit_scopus_norm																			
avg_cit_gs_norm													+	+	+	+	+		
art_wos_int		-	-	-														There is no evidence of a positive impact on the internationalization of the publication.	
mnisw_wos_avg							NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA							
mnisw_scopus_avg							NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA						There is no evidence for determining the impact on the average publication score assigned to journals by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education.	
n_pat	+	+		+			+	+		+		+					+		
any_pat	+	+		+		+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+				+		
n_pat_pol	+	+	+	+	+	+			+		+	+					+		
n_proj																		There is no evidence for determining the impact on the acquisition of subsequent grants.	
n_nagr		+							-	-			+	+	+	+	+		

* In the case of RDD, only significant effects in all three variants of compartment width were considered significant.

** ATT—Average Treatment Effect on the Treated.

*** LATE—Local Average Treatment Effect.

Source: Own study.

 p < 0.1 + Positive effect
 p < 0.05 - Negative effect
 p < 0.01 ON The effect was not estimated due to missing data

